

Shipping spills and plastic pollution: A review of maritime governance in the North Sea

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ABSTRACT

Plastic pollution of our oceans from land-based sources and shipping spills raises concerns for marine ecosystems, maritime industries and human health. This paper examines the systems and processes in place in the case of plastic pollution due to a shipping spill in the North Sea and the instruments and mechanisms to hold polluters accountable. A desk-based analysis was conducted, and 11 expert interviews contextualised the desk findings. From the 263 reported incidents from 1917 to 2021, 39 % of the reported container loss cases occurred in, or near, the North Sea. Fragmented jurisdiction, frail and uncoordinated policies, aid the shipping sector to deflect responsibility. Around 62 % of the obstacles mentioned by the interviewees addressed governance, including, notably, the lack of international measures, and regulations on shipping routes to protect sensitive areas. The study also identifies the difficulty to enforce compensation for the damage made to ecosystems and biodiversity.

1. Introduction

On the night of January 1st 2019, a storm caused the vessel MSC Zoe to move violently and lose 342 containers weighing approximately 3257 t into the sea. Diverse consumer packaged goods (CPG) and packaging material were spilled in the waters and washed ashore on the Dutch coastline and on the Dutch and German Wadden Islands ([Dutch Safety Board, 2020a](#)). It is believed that to this day, a quarter of the debris that fell from MSC Zoe remains in the North Sea ([Stichting Noordzee, 2021](#)).

Plastics are widely traded across the globe, a process in which oceans play an important role: around 90 % of global trade of goods between countries takes place via cargo shipping ([United Nations, 2017](#)). One of the busiest trading routes is in the North Sea, from the English Channel to the Skagerrak strait, which includes the largest port in Europe, the Port of Rotterdam in the Netherlands ([NorthSEE, 2018](#)).

Plastics have become a predominant material in modern society. They can be shaped in different forms for a variety of CPG, and are used in various economic sectors, including the textile industry, healthcare, agriculture and transport ([Napper and Thompson, 2020](#)). Being versatile, lightweight, solid, corrosion-resistant and inexpensive, plastics evidently benefit society ([Napper and Thompson, 2020](#)). Yet, plastics' over-production and accumulation during the last century, which is also labelled the "Plastic Age", has led to negative environmental and

societal consequences ([Napper and Thompson, 2020](#); [Thompson et al., 2009](#)). In 2010, an estimated 4.8 to 12.7 million t of plastic entered the oceans from waste generated on land ([Jambeck et al., 2015](#)). A decade later, it was estimated that 75 % of all marine litter contained plastics ([Napper and Thompson, 2020](#)). It can take decades for man-made plastics to fully decompose, especially in marine waters, where weathering mechanisms are altered ([Gutow, 2015](#)). Plastics' impact at sea has prompted concerns over their significance for marine ecosystems, human health, and maritime industries ([Napper and Thompson, 2020](#)).

Plastic contamination of our oceans occurs via rivers and canals, sewage discharge, litter from ships at sea, and shipping spills ([Leslie et al., 2017](#)). According to the World Shipping Council, an annual average of 1382 containers are reported to be lost at sea, an equivalent of 13,820 t of CPG each year ([World Shipping Council, 2020](#); [National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, 2014](#)). Fragmented jurisdiction, frail and uncoordinated policies can lead to a deflection of responsibility by the shipping sector ([Dauvergne, 2018](#)). In parallel, the melting of arctic sea ice caused by global warming can potentially widen the shipping areas and further increase traffic in the Northern sea routes ([United Nations, 2016](#)). Therefore, the prolific application of plastic in CPG, combined with the potential increase in trade and traffic, may lead to more container spills, and, consequently, an increase in marine plastic pollution. This increase in container losses can affect the provision of critical marine ecosystem services such as fisheries and recreation

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(Beaumont et al., 2019). Described as the “new millennium's Tragedy of the Commons” by Vince and Hardesty, marine litter has shed light on the need for responsible management of the oceans (Vince and Hardesty, 2018).

These developments justify an evaluation of maritime governance in the North Sea regarding the loss of containers. Historically, North Sea States raised concerns on the effects of discharge of harmful substances and dumping at sea during the first of the North Sea Conferences (NSC), held in London in 1987. Under the umbrella of the Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic (OSPAR), the current legislative instrument regulating the North Sea region, the NSC led to the adoption of several Principles, including the Precautionary Principle, the Ecosystem Approach and the Polluter Pays Principle, in national regulations, as well as within binding Conventions (OSPAR Commission, 2021a).

This paper aims to improve our understanding of the legal and policy systems and processes in place in the case of plastic pollution due to a shipping spill in the North Sea. Furthermore, it aims to examine the instruments and mechanisms to hold polluters liable, and to assess whether the NSC Principles are, in fact, translated into measures. Applying the multilevel governance approach, five levels of governance intersecting in North Sea were examined: (1) global,¹ (2) European level,² (3) regional,³ (4) national,⁴ and (5) private sector and civil society.

2. Methods and materials

To describe and review the systems and processes in the North Sea when a container is lost overboard, this research used a mixed research methodology. First, a desk-based analysis was performed of scientific peer-reviewed literature, grey literature, and newspaper archives, applying a systematic literature review method. Second, a route density map was designed using an online tool. Third, a series of semi-structured interviews were conducted with relevant stakeholders and experts to contextualise, verify and validate some of the findings of the systematic literature review.

2.1. Systematic literature review method

As part of the desk-based analysis, an extensive worldwide casualty list from 1917 to 2021 (Appendix A) was compiled to better understand the issue of container loss in the North Sea. The analysis assessed: 1) the occurrence of spills in the North Sea, in comparison to other regions; 2) how many spills occurred in proximity of the North Sea, and could have potentially affected its waters; and 3) how many of the spills that happened in or near the North Sea were container loss cases.

Based on the systematic literature review method, the protocol consisted of combined inclusion and exclusion parameters. Inclusion parameters were: shipping spills that resulted in spillage at sea, including rivers, ports and harbours, providing the spills affected sea waters. Exclusion parameters were: leisure or cruise ships, and spills due to a deliberate discharge or due to an act of war or terrorism. Also, spills that occurred in high seas, under unclear State jurisdiction, were excluded. Hundreds of reported spills were reviewed and analysed by cross-referencing multiple sources from renowned institutions with authority on maritime pollution, such as the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), Cedre and International Tanker Owners Pollution Federation (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, 2014; Cedre, 2021; International Tanker Owners Pollution Federation, 2020). The exact location of the spills that were in accordance

with the parameters was reaffirmed using Google dynamic map (Google Maps, 2021).

The spills were listed chronologically per region, and only those with a known month, year and location were included. A principal division was made between “North Sea and Surrounding Areas” and “Other Areas”, which are areas located further away from the North Sea, and therefore not considered a direct threat in the case of a shipping spill. “North Sea and Surrounding Areas” included the North Sea, the English Channel, the Kattegat and Øresund straits, the Celtic Sea and the Bay of Biscay, and the Baltic Sea. “Other Areas” included the Mediterranean Sea, the Black Sea, the rest of the North Atlantic Ocean, the South Atlantic Ocean, the Indian Ocean, and the Pacific Ocean.

A main distinction was made according to the type of spill: 1) oil, which is generally transported on purpose-built ships (tankers) and 2) containers. Certain incidents, where oil was spilled in addition to containers, were considered container spills since the products were transported in cargo ships. The contents of the containers lost were also mentioned in the list. CPG stands for all sorts of consumer-packaged goods (involving plastics), HNS stands for Hazardous and Noxious Substances, and “Containers (Unknown)” refers to incidents where information on the content spilled was not available.

2.2. Route density for cargo vessels

The map presented in Fig. 1 was designed using European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) Human Activities' tool, which is based on Association for Information Systems (AIS) technology and maps by the European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA), to provide an overview of cargo ships' route density along the North Sea. ESMA's method restores the trajectory of each ship based on recorded positions and by counting the routes crossing in each cell of a grid during a selected time. To build a route density map, the grids have a definition of 1 × 1 km (EMODnet, 2019). Inclusion parameters were: routes per square kilometre during the month of May 2021, route density in the North Sea region; and solely cargo vessels, excluding all other types of vessels. Two location pins were added to indicate the route from the English Channel to the Skagerrak strait. An anchor symbol was added to represent each of the four largest cargo ports, in terms of the total tonnage and volume of containers handled.

2.3. Key-informant interviews

As part of the third research method, for a more complete understanding of the problem, 11 key-informant interviews were conducted, audio-recorded, and transcribed. Ten of the interviews were conducted via video-conferencing and one interview was held in person. The interviews addressed accountability mechanisms, levels of governance, marine litter and, additionally, the MSC Zoe case, in the Netherlands. The interview method comprised both, a set of specific questions and open-ended questions (Appendix C). Two slightly different questionnaires were drafted, to adapt to the participants' profiles. Three of the interviewees had expertise at two levels of governance. To simplify, interviewees with regional and national expertise were named “National”, since they both represent the Netherlands in regional Conventions. One interviewee with global and regional expertise was named “Global”, for a better distribution at all levels. The interviewees were: Global (1), EU (2), Regional (1), National and Local (3), Maritime Law (3), and Marine Science (1) (Appendix B).

A qualitative analysis of the interviews was conducted using Atlas.ti software for Mac. The participants' views on liability and the perceived obstacles to efficient governance were analysed. A codebook was created according to the approach developed by Saldaña (2013). After a preliminary reading of the transcripts, Open Coding was used as a starting point, to establish provisional analytical leads that can be further explored. Process Coding was applied to create codes gradually while going through the transcripts and selecting elements linked to the

¹ “Global” refers to the international or worldwide level.

² “European” refers to the European Union and its Member States.

³ “Regional” refers to the countries that surround the North Sea.

⁴ “National” refers to the country of the Netherlands.

Fig. 1. Route density for cargo vessels in May 2021.
Source: Own map by author using [EMODnet \(2021\)](#) Human Activities.

code groups. To avoid redundancy, similar codes and code groups were merged in the second cycle of coding, leading to a final number of 22 codes applicable under four code groups.

2.4. Limitations

This research faced a few limitations. The spills analysed were solely spills that were reported and on which information was found. The possibility of an even larger number of unreported spills remains. Due to time-constraints, the number of interviews was limited, and potentially less representative on a larger scale. Moreover, initiatives on marine litter are relatively recent, and even though they seem relevant, more time is needed to assess if they will address the subject of container loss.

3. Results

3.1. Shipping casualties over time

The North Sea is bordered by the coastlines of the European Union (EU) countries of France, Belgium, the Netherlands, Germany, Denmark and Sweden; and the non-EU countries of Norway and the United Kingdom (England and Scotland) ([European Environment Agency, 2017](#)). The North Sea is renowned for maritime trade and one of the busiest seas in the world, especially on the route from the English Channel to the Skagerrak strait ([NorthSEE, 2018](#)). As shown in [Fig. 1](#), the highest density of traffic by cargo vessels in May 2021 is located on this route ([EMODnet, 2021](#)). The largest cargo ports in the EU North Sea, are the ports of Antwerp, Hamburg, Bremen-Bremerhaven, and the largest port in Europe, the Port of Rotterdam ([Eurostat, 2017](#)).

There was a total of 263 reported incidents from December 1917 to May 2021, of which 138 were container spills and 125 were oil spills. From these 263 incidents, 35 spills took place in the North Sea ([Appendix A](#)). This number amounts to 13.3 % of the total number of reported spills worldwide, and places the North Sea, which covers approximately 0.75 million km², in fourth position after the North

Atlantic Ocean (18.6 %), which covers around 41.49 million km²; the Pacific Ocean (17.9 %), which covers around 161.76 million km²; and the area of the Celtic Sea, Bay of Biscay (14.1 %), which covers a rough estimate of 0.52 million km² ([OSPAR Commission, 2022](#); [Tools and S. I. To, n.d.](#)). These regions have witnessed the highest amounts of spills during the past decade ([Fig. 2](#)). Moreover, 10 out of the 35 reported spills in the North Sea affected the Netherlands ([Appendix A](#)). The North Sea is not only one of the busiest seas, it is also considered a shallow sea, which is deeper in the North, and an area with strong currents, which could explain the number of incidents in the region ([European Environment Agency, 2017](#)) [Interview 2].

Additionally, nine spills in the North Sea affected nearby areas such as the English Channel, the Skagerrak strait, the Norwegian Sea and the Wadden Sea. Also, 20 out of the 35 reported spills in the North Sea were container loss incidents, of which five involved CPG and three of the lost containers were carrying unknown contents ([Appendix A](#)).

Furthermore, from the 138 container spills worldwide, 34 happened in proximity of the North Sea ([Appendix A](#)), with 11 cases in the English Channel, four cases in the Kattegat and Øresund straits, and, further away, 12 cases in the Celtic Sea and Bay of Biscay, and seven cases in the Baltic Sea. This means that 39 % of the total reported container loss cases since 1917 occurred in, or near, the North Sea.

3.2. Multilevel governance

There are various levels of governance in the North Sea: global agreements, EU, regional agreements, national and local governments, private sector and civil society. As shown in [Fig. 3](#), each level of governance has its own systems and processes, as well as applicable policies and measures, when confronted by the issue of container loss. The following sections explain these instruments for each governance level.

Fig. 2. Treemap representing the number of spills per region from 1917 until 2021.

3.3. Global agreements

International maritime governance is generally guided by the UN and specifically the International Maritime Organization (IMO) [Interview 3, Interview 11]. The Torrey Canyon oil spill in 1967 was the world's first spill to draw the attention of the public on marine pollution from ships (The International Tanker Owners Pollution Federation Limited, 2014). It was the catalyst for moving IMO into environmental and legal issues and for sparking public and scientific concern about the potential effects of contaminants in the sea (International Maritime Organization, 2009; Wells, 2017; Comité Maritime International, 1967). The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) defines the Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs) of its Member States, and their respective rights, maritime boundaries, and responsibilities upon uses of the oceans (NorthSEE, 2018) [Interview 11]. Three categories fall under most of the IMO Conventions: "maritime safety, the prevention of marine pollution, and liability and compensation". Member Parties' governments have the responsibility to enforce the IMO Conventions (International Maritime Organization, 2011a). A Convention or amendment needs the support of a majority of Member States to be adopted (International Maritime Organization, 2011a) [Interview 3]. Thus, proposals, negotiations, and the development of new measures are a lengthy process [Interview 3, Interview 4]. Concluded and signed in Brussels, the 1952 Arrest Convention is a multilateral agreement to unify rules of law on the arrest of ships. Upon breach of a domestic law, an arrest can be made in the jurisdiction of the port State, provided the vessel and the port State are both parties to the Convention (High Contracting Parties and Government of Belgium, 1952). In 2012, the World Bank Group published the International Finance Corporation's (IFC) Guidance Notes which were designed to assist the World Bank Group's clients and IFC staff to meet the IFC performance standards

related to environmental and social sustainability, and to assess and manage the environmental and social risks of their activities, including potential grievances from affected communities (World Bank Group, 2012).

A legal regime is determined according to the type of pollution detected [Interview 8, Interview 9]. The main issues emerging from the Torrey Canyon incident, and from the Amoco Cadiz oil spill in 1978, were to determine who is responsible for the damage caused by a spill, and to quantify the extent of indemnifications to be compensated (International Maritime Organization, 2009; Rares, 2018; Bonnieux and Rainelli, 1993; Cedre, 2018). During the Amoco Cadiz court proceedings, several categories of claims were substantially reduced by the court for exaggeration, lack of evidence or the inability to prove a causal connection between the damage and the Amoco parties (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, 1983). Other categories, such as ecological damage, lost image and enjoyment were deemed unrecognisable and eliminated (Gundlach, 1989). Liability mechanisms for oil spills have changed since the Amoco Cadiz incident. A causal link between oil spilled and a vessel can now be easily established via fingerprint methods [Interview 2]. Once a causal link between the damage and the vessel is established, the accountability process is straightforward, and usually results in monetary compensation for the clean-up costs, which can include the cleaning of oiled animals, and property losses, if documentation is provided [Interview 2, Interview 8]. Prompted by the Torrey Canyon and the Amoco Cadiz accidents, the International Convention on Civil Liability for Oil Pollution Damage (CLC), established in 1969, and the International Oil Pollution Compensation (IOPC) Fund, established in 1992, ensure that adequate compensation is available to the victims of the oil spill (International Maritime Organization, 2009; Cedre, 2018). The IOPC Fund raised the compensation limit for future oil spills, and the aftermath of the Amoco Cadiz spill

Fig. 3. Landscape of the relevant policies and measures intersecting in the North Sea.

influenced the subsequent 2003 protocol (Cedre, 2018). These conventions provide a strict liability over the owner, at the exception of acts of terrorism, when an attack on the vessel caused the spill [Interview 8]. In cases such as the Prestige or the Erika oil spills, it was also possible to hold other entities liable, such as the company who hired the ship and the classification society, because Prestige, for instance, was not deemed sea-worthy [Interview 2]. The IMO also adopted an additional regime which includes bunker oil spills from vessels, in addition to tankers (International Maritime Organization, 2009).

Effective since December 31, 2004, the International Convention for the Safety of Life at Sea (SOLAS) Regulation V/19 requires AIS to be fitted aboard all ships of more than 300 gross tonnage (International Maritime Organization, 2020a). AIS enables the monitoring and tracking of ship movement and shipping traffic (NorthSEE, 2018). This system helps find the ship and its owner through the vessels register [Interview 9]. Still, as seen in the Hansa Carrier case in 1990 and the Ever Laurel case in 1992, when not reported or witnessed, containers lost overboard require further investigation to establish a causal link between the pollution and the vessel [Interview 8]. The Ever Laurel, owned by Evergreen Marine Corporation, was transporting children's bath toys from Hong Kong to Washington, when 29,000 floating plastic toys fell overboard in the central Pacific (Ebbesmeyer et al., 2007; Business Insider and Guenot, 2021). Plastic turtles, ducks, frogs, and beavers, which have become known as the "Friendly Floatees", travelled through the Bering Strait and into the Arctic until the first toys were seen 10 months later off the coast of Alaska. Toys had been found in all various places, and a rubber duck even reached a beach in Massachusetts 11 years later (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, 2014; Hohn, 2012). The spill was not reported by the Ever Laurel and for years the identity of the ship was not revealed, until Journalist Donovan Hohn identified it as the Evergreen Ever Laurel by consulting old shipping schedules and by cross-referencing with the coordinates found using the Ocean Surface Current Simulator (OSCURS) simulation (Business Insider

and Guenot, 2021; Hohn, 2012). Many ships follow the same routes, and cargo casualties can be more complex than oil since they cannot be easily traced to the vessel with fingerprinting [Interview 2, Interview 9]. Containers usually carry a variety of CPG and plastic is a heterogeneous material [Interview 6]. For instance, the composition of high-density polyethylene (HDPE) pellets can vary due to their additives and production process [Interview 6]. Currents can also move lost containers from the place of the incident to other countries and jurisdictions, thereby further complicating the linkage with a vessel (Hohn, 2012) [Interview 8].

Concerning clean-up operations and costs, the Nairobi International Convention on the Removal of Wrecks (2007) was adopted to harmonise rules and procedures for States to remove, or have removed shipwrecks that may pose a hazard to navigation, people's safety, properties at sea, or the marine environment (International Maritime Organization, 2019a) [Interview 5]. In principle, the owner is liable for the costs of locating and removing the ship and containers lost at sea (International Maritime Organization, 2019a). One of the reasons for holding the owner liable is that the owner can be located via the registered ship, whereas crew members and ship operators can change in the next port [Interview 9]. If the owner does not undertake the removal of the wreck and the mitigation costs, this responsibility will be taken by the State where the spill has occurred, and legal actions might follow [Interview 5]. As a side note, as seen in the MV Wakashio oil spill in 2020, the liability of the ship-owner under the 2001 CLC can be limited by the Convention on Limitation of Liability for Maritime Claims (LLMC), a Convention based on the tonnage carried by ships that entitles owners and insurers to limit their liability for claims over a certain tonnage (International Maritime Organization, 1976). Mauritius being party to the LLMC Protocol 1976, the limits in a Mauritius court is limited at 13 million Special Drawing Right (SDR), which is about 15.6 million euros, even though Japan is party to LLMC Protocol 96, which has a limit of 46.5 million SDR (International Maritime Organization, 2020b). Thus,

only 1 billion yen (about 7.5 million euros) was paid in financial contribution in a joint fund between Mitsui O.S.K. Lines and ship-owner Nagashiki Shipping for the spill (Yamaguchi, 2020).

Furthermore, a container loss can be due to negligent blocking, bracing and lashing of cargo (International Maritime Organization, 2014a) [Interview 3]. In 1972 the International Convention for Safe Containers issued uniform safety regulations and procedures for the inspection, approval and maintenance of containers, to be implemented by Member States (International Maritime Organization, 2020c). The Amoco Cadiz spill highlighted the fragilities of the IMO instruments, and it led to their re-examination, and the participation of more States (Cedre, 2018; Lucchini, 1985). This resulted in the adoption of the 1978 MARPOL Protocol, which absorbed the parent Convention 1973 MARPOL (International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships), and introduced significant adjustments and tighter controls (International Maritime Organization, 2014b). The spill also led to the International Convention on Salvage by IMO (Cedre, 2018). Additional safety and pollution audits were added to the “Hague Memorandum” in 1978, which were mainly focused on the living and working conditions on ships, as required by the International Labour Organization (ILO) (Paris MoU, 2021; International Labor Organisation, 1976). This case motivated the establishment of the Paris Memorandum of Understanding on Port State Control (Paris MoU) in 1982, which is signed by 14 European Countries and covers the safety of marine life, the prevention of pollution by ships and shipboard conditions (Paris MoU, 2021). Ten years later, the IMO Assembly adopted the Code of Safe Practice for Cargo Stowage and Securing (CSS Code), which was later amended in 2011, to provide a global standard for the safe stowage and securing of cargoes. The CSS Code draws attention to the responsibility of the ship-owners and the ship operators to ensure the vessel is suitable for its purpose. It also stresses the responsibility of the ship Master to ensure the safe conduct of the journey, as well as the supervision of the lashing and securing of the cargo (International Maritime Organization, 2011b).

An official investigation on the causes of the MSC Napoli cargo spill was conducted by the Marine Accident Investigation Branch (MAIB) in 2008, and raised questions on the vessel's structure and safety precautions. The container audit showed that the containers were 20 % overweight, about 312 t heavier than the declared weights. The MAIB believed that this led to reduced safety margin between the listing and the strength of the hull. Among the recommendations on safety issues, MAIB noted that the required report to classification societies under the SOLAS Regulation VI/2, which should include structural damage, cracking and weld repairs on main structural parts of a vessel, is either “not fully understood or occasionally overlooked”. MAIB added that if the ship manager had disclosed the status of the defect, it may have led to an informed decision on whether or not the vessel was fit to sail (Marine Accident Investigation Branch, 2008). The findings of the investigation led to the voluntary “Safe Transport of Containers by Sea: Guidelines on Best Practices” guidelines and the subsequent amendments to SOLAS regulation VI/2, which require the compulsory verification of the gross mass of containers prior to packing, and the submission of the verified weight of the vessel by the shipper to his flag State and to the marine terminal (World Shipping Council, 2013; International Maritime Organization, 2019b).

Additionally, the 2014 IMO/ILO/UNECE Code of Practice for Packing of Cargo Transport Units (CTU Code) was developed, as a voluntary code of practice for the handling and loading of containers for transportation by sea. It addresses the misdeclaration of containers' weight and overloading, the consideration of suitable containers for specific contents, the correct labelling of packages; and provides a guide for blocking and lashing, for load distribution, and for stacking heights and limitations (International Maritime Organization, 2014a). On the topic of container weight, the Paris MoU requires port States controls to ensure the compliance of ship-owners to the guidelines laid down by the international Conventions (Paris MoU, 2021). It should be noted that, according to these guidelines, Hazardous and Noxious Substances (HNS)

should be placed near the door for the safety of the crew and the ship itself (International Maritime Organization, 2014a) [Interview 3]. Thus, these are the first containers to fall when a ship loses balance [Interview 3]. Plastics and plastic pellets are mentioned in the CTU Code Appendix in “friction factors”, but not as harmful substances (International Maritime Organization, 2014a). Yet, when in contact with sea water, plastics form biofilms that leach off different types of toxic chemicals. Among the chemicals leaked, Bisphenol A, phthalates and flame retardants, routinely used in CPG, have been proven to disrupt the endocrine system, and can potentially cause hormonal cancers and metabolic disorders (Campanale et al., 2020). Also, the leaching of plastics is harder to contain in comparison to oil, which can be contained via floating structures [Interview 4, Interview 6]. Additionally, small sized CPG, such as HDPE pellets, are practically impossible to completely remove [Interview 3].

MARPOL Annex V, which entered into force in 1988, concerns the prevention of pollution from oil, HNS, atmospheric pollution, sewage and garbage (NorthSEE, 2018; International Maritime Organization, 1998). Annex V prohibits the release of all garbage at sea from ships, which includes plastics, and thereby addresses marine litter (European Union, 2016; Marine Environment Protection Committee, 2017). But while Annex V includes garbage discharge, it excludes discharge of plastics due to container loss. Furthermore, Annex V defines certain areas as “Special Areas” in which higher degrees of protection are required, which includes the North Sea since 1991. Special Areas need to be further protected for their oceanographical, ecological and traffic conditions (International Maritime Organization, 2019c). Another protective tool available to Member States is the PSSA designation. Under an IMO treaty Particularly Sensitive Sea Areas (PSSAs) must be avoided via the Vessel Traffic Services (International Maritime Organization, 2020b).

Marine litter related to lost containers has only recently appeared on the global agenda [Interview 10]. The UN GloLitter Partnerships Project proposed the marking of fishing gear so it can be traced back to the vessel, and the avoidance of single-use plastics (International Maritime Organization, 2019d). Nonetheless, the marking of containers, also via technologies, to trace them when lost, or to facilitate their recovery, was not mentioned. To further develop MARPOL Annex V, the Marine Environment Protection Committee (MEPC) of IMO adopted an Action Plan to include marine plastic litter from sea-based activities, and to meet the targets of the 2030 Sustainable Development Goals 14 on the oceans. The Plan, which should be completed by 2025, inserts the proposal of a compulsory system to declare the loss of containers at sea, as well as to ascertain the number of losses (International Maritime Organization, 2018).

3.4. European Union

The EU is party to the UNCLOS Convention and ensures that the EU directives reflect the obligations set by it (NorthSEE, 2018). Even though the EU Directives are binding, the EU relies on Member States to enforce the Directives in their national laws [Interview 1]. For instance, the Vessel Traffic Monitoring and Information System Directive (2002/59/EC) was adopted in 2002 to support the cooperation between the coastal stations of Member States for the reporting of lost or spotted containers at sea through the central SafeSeaNet⁵ system (The European Parliament and the Council of the European Union, 2002). Yet, to ensure the common application of MARPOL Annex V at European level, and to ensure that offences can be prosecutable in criminal law, several Directives

⁵ Operational 24 h a day, the SafeSeaNet is an electronic exchange system for port and maritime safety, the protection of marine environment and efficient maritime traffic and transport. The SafeSeaNet network links all national SafeSeaNet systems in a central system that facilitates data exchange between Member States, and provides the Commission with relevant information.

were adopted by the EU (European Union, 2016). The Protection of the Environment through Criminal Law (Directive 2008/99/EC) mandates the prosecution of States for damage to water quality, animals and plants (European Union, 2016). In addition, the 2004/35/CE Environmental Liability Directive (ELD), a framework based on the Polluter Pays Principle, covers the prevention and mitigation of environmental damage caused by the discharge of HNS (The European Parliament and the Council of the European Union, 2004) [Interview 2]. Yet again, plastics are excluded from the HNS list. Also, the ELD requires responsible parties to fund the remediation measures necessary, and to bring back nature to baseline-position. However, in practice, and as seen in the Torrey Canyon and in the Amoco Cadiz cases, this sort of regime is often challenging to apply due to lack of expertise, specifically for measuring non-values. To use the ELD and hold responsible parties liable for the damage on nature and ecosystem services, data on baseline conditions should be available to prove losses due to the plastic spill [Interview 2]. Regarding MARPOL Annex V, the Port Reception Facilities Directive (2000/59/EC) covers the collection of waste from ships visiting a port and aims to reduce ship-generated waste (The European Parliament and the Council of the European Union, 2019). Moreover, the European Commission Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC) qualifies the substances and objects as waste only if the holder intends or is required to discard them (The European Parliament and the Council of the European Union, 2018) [Interview 1]. Until now, no specific legislations address accidental container loss at the EU level [Interview 1].

Furthermore, States are required to monitor the quality of the marine environment, including marine litter. Adopted in 2008, the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) is a policy-instrument that can be further developed and adapted via national laws by Member States (Karasik et al., 2020) [Interview 1]. One of the MSFD Descriptors focuses on the monitoring of marine litter, to ensure it does not harm the marine and coastal environment. Because of this Descriptor, single-use plastics were identified by the Member States as one of the most commonly found materials on coasts. This data provided the basis for the ban on single-use plastics, the Single-Use Plastics Directive, which is part of the European Green Deal on climate change (European Commission, 2019a; European Commission, 2018) [Interview 1, Interview 11]. Moreover, the European Chemicals Agency, under the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) Regulation has requested the restriction of microplastics as an intentionally added material. Restricting microplastics in CPG, including cosmetics, detergents and medical applications, could reduce marine pollution (European Commission, 2019b).

3.5. Regional agreements

To protect the North Sea, two main regional agreements were formed to unify the efforts against pollution. The Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic (the OSPAR Convention) adopted in 1992, absorbed the Oslo Convention of 1972 against dumping from sea-based activities and the Paris Conventions of 1974 against land-based sources of marine pollution (UNEP, 2021; OSPAR Convention, 2018) [Interview 11]. Also, an Annex was adopted in 1998 to cover non-polluting human activities that can affect marine life. Fifteen States are party to the OSPAR Convention, including the EU North Sea countries Denmark, Germany, the Netherlands, Belgium, Luxembourg, and France. Non-EU countries in the North Sea basin have their own measures, which are not subjected to the EU Directives. The measures that OSPAR States have in common are pursuant to the OSPAR Commission, the EEZs and the international regulations [Interview 11]. OSPAR requires from each Contracting Party that they ensure incidents are reported to the authorities, and that if they receive such a report they alert any other Contracting Party concerned. Annex III also reinforces the duty of the Commission to assess and list which substances are noxious, persistent and accumulative, and to draw up guidelines and procedures to prevent and eliminate pollution (OSPAR Convention,

2018). Nevertheless, the OSPAR Convention excludes plastics from the list of substances for consideration.

Second, the Bonn Agreement, effective since 1978, aims to protect the North Sea from accidental and illegal oil pollution. It works jointly with MARPOL and enforces the recent MARPOL Annex VI for sulphur and nitrogen oxides (Bonn Agreement, 2001). The revised Bonn Agreement does not mention plastics either.

In its Bergen Statement in 2010, OSPAR expressed its commitment to the Precautionary Principle and to the establishment of Marine Protected Areas (OSPAR Commission, 2010). In 2014, the Regional Action Plan (RAP) was developed for the prevention and management of marine litter, for the period of 2014–2021. RAP is composed of several Actions, which are divided in four themes: “Actions to prevent sea-based sources of marine litter, Actions to prevent land-based sources of marine litter, Removal Action, Education and Outreach”. Actions to prevent sea-based sources of marine litter ensure the implementation of the Port Reception Facilities Directive and assist the revision of the EU Directives. RAP also supports MARPOL Annex V by addressing ship-generated waste, the Paris MoU by prioritising port State inspections, and the North Sea Network of Investigators and Prosecutors by analysing penalties and fines issued by Contracting Parties (OSPAR Commission, 2014). Also, OSPAR is involved in clean-up projects such as the Fishing for Litter initiative and has developed several indicators in line with the MSFD to monitor and assess beach litter, plastic particles in biota, seabed litter and microplastics (OSPAR Commission, 2014) [Interview 3].

3.6. National and local governments: close-up on the Netherlands

In the Netherlands, hauliers are required to notify the shipping line of the weight of containers prior to loading, and vessels have a duty to report incidents to the Human Environment and Transport Inspectorate (ILT). In addition, insurance for wreck removal is mandatory. After a spill, the ILT, and sometimes the Dutch Safety Board, carry out an investigation (Netherlands Enterprise Agency RVO, 2021). Dutch police, the fire brigade and the municipalities work jointly together under the Dutch Safety Regions Act. The Act was created to extend multidisciplinary cooperation for the management of emergency crises and disasters (Dutch Ministry of Security and Justice, 2010). This Act was set in motion for the clean-up operation of the MSC Zoe incident in 2019 (Dutch Safety Board, 2020a) [Interview 3].

The MCS Zoe accident was classified as a severe casualty as defined by the Casualty Investigation Code of the IMO and the Directive 2009/18/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of April 23, 2009, which establishes the basis of an investigation of casualties in the maritime transport sector (International Maritime Organization, 2019b; Dutch Safety Board, 2020b; European Parliament and European Council, 2009). The marine safety investigation authorities of the three states, the flag State Panama and the coastal States of Germany and the Netherlands, agreed to collaborate on the investigation, with Panama leading the investigation. In the meantime, floating and sunken containers posed a threat to the shipping route and ships were redirected to another route by a guard vessel. Vessel-owner MSC was contacted by the Directorate-General for Public Works and Water Management (Rijkswaterstaat) and informed of its liability for the recovery of the lost cargo, after which MSC appointed a salvage company. Netherlands Coastguards, Rijkswaterstaat and the salvage company drew an emergency plan to recover the containers. Since the ship crew was not aware of what was being carried, it took more than 24 h to establish the number of containers lost (Dutch Safety Board, 2020a) [Interview 2, Interview 10]. Kommunernes International Miljøorganisation or KIMO, an association of coastal municipalities from eight countries, including the Netherlands, organised the Fishing for Litter scheme together with fishing associations to collect marine litter for processing. However, the amount of litter from the spill exceeded the capacity of the scheme, and additional funding was requested from the Dutch authorities [Interview

3].

Concerning claims and liability, the Netherlands is party to the 1910 Collision Convention and to the CLC Protocol, as well as the IFC Protocol (Van Traa Advocaten, 2017). According to Dutch law, a container loss by a vessel and the damage caused are akin to the Collision or Allision⁶ rules (Van Traa Advocaten, 2017) [Interview 8]. Collision liability pursuant to the Dutch legal grounds is channelled towards the vessel's owner [Interview 8]. Moreover, the ELD could cover losses of non-values, such as nature and ecosystems. Yet, there is limited practice in the Netherlands with these types of cases [Interview 2]. As seen in the MSC Zoe incident, long-term environmental externalities were not calculated, nor compensated for [Interview 3]. The MSC and its insurer, paid 3.4 million euros in compensation for the damages and provided the guarantee they would pay 7 million euros for remediation measures, regardless of direct causal proof (Dutch Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management, 2021). Still, according to a press release by Stichting Noordzee on January 2, 2021, an approximate of 800 t of the debris remains in the North Sea, requiring a clean-up operation that might not be covered by MSC (Stichting Noordzee, 2021). This may be due to the dynamic nature of the Wadden Sea, where strong currents and sand prevented the recovery of all the containers [Interview 2].

Additionally, the Netherlands is party to the Nairobi International Convention under the "Maritime Accident Response"; and to the LLMC. Nonetheless, in regards to the LLMC, Dutch authorities have opened the possibility of establishing a separate wreck removal fund for the removal of wrecks and cargo (Van Traa Advocaten, 2017). During the MSC Zoe case, which is considered a modern example of the Dutch accountability process, Rijkswaterstaat collected all the claims from the affected municipalities and filed one central claim towards the insurer. This may have contributed to a rapid conflict resolution [Interview 5]. In comparison, in Denmark, claims from the State and from private individuals are brought to court separately [Interview 9].

Prior to proceedings, the Dutch State assesses whether the ship-owner can pay for the remediation and the damage costs. Usually, the vessel is arrested and the affiliated Protection and Indemnity Insurance (P&I) Club⁷ is contacted for guarantees. Under Dutch law, and according to the Arrest Convention 1952, vessel arrest or sister-vessel⁸ arrest can be applied when the owner is liable for a legal claim (Van Traa Advocaten, 2017). However, the P&I Clubs have a "Pay to be Paid" rule.⁹ This rule can be problematic when the owner of a vessel does not have the means to pay for the claims [Interview 8]. And, while ships are required to report container loss to their flag State authority, if the incident was not witnessed, they might not come forward for fear of reprisal [Interview 8, Interview 10].

Listed as a World Heritage Site, a Natura 2000 site, and a PSSA, the Wadden Sea extends along the coasts of Denmark, Germany and the Netherlands (Dutch Safety Board, 2020a). The Wadden Sea Area, which is a zone of joint governance, is managed by the Common Wadden Sea Secretariat (Bonn Agreement, 2001) [Interview 7]. The Secretariat generally follows the IMO guidelines and the Bonn Agreement, and supports the enforcement of the Port Reception Facilities Directive at the Wadden Sea harbours. One of the challenges faced by the Secretariat is to communicate the degree of sensitivity of the area and its importance on a global scale, to convince the IMO to prioritise protective measures. To protect the area and the Dutch Wadden Islands, the Secretariat must reinforce its position as World Heritage Site and as a PSSA, and have

⁶ The allision rule refers to any damage caused without there having been a collision.

⁷ P&I Clubs are insurance associations that provide coverage and handle liability claims for ship-owners.

⁸ A sister-vessel is another vessel, different from the one involved in the claim, registered under the same owner.

⁹ The "Pay to be Paid" rule requires the owner of the vessel involved in the claim to first pay the plaintiff(s), to be paid by the P&I Club.

agreed on common shipping and safety measures, under a trilateral policy cooperation [Interview 7]. To this day, the use of the northerly route instead of the precautionary area is a non-mandatory recommendation (NorthSEE, 2018) [Interview 3]. Lobbying at IMO for designed shipping route is ongoing, although, due to the pace of the IMO processes, these measures might be enforced on the long-term [Interview 3, Interview 5]. Further research is being made on the future effects of the MSC Zoe spill on the Wadden islands' ecosystems and biodiversity, and on whether the compensation paid will be sufficient to mitigate their costs (Dutch Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management, 2021).

On a provincial level, marine litter and circular economy¹⁰ are more than ever on the Dutch organisations' agenda (Foundation, 2016) [Interview 10]. The North Sea Commission of the Conference of Peripheral Maritime Regions of Europe (CPMR), in cooperation with Dutch provinces, promotes and creates awareness in the North Sea region, and is also active in the policy sphere. The Action Plan 2020–2022 covers different Thematic Groups, and one of them, the Marine Resources Group, involves tackling marine litter, lobbying for more regulations to track containers, and improving policies on circular production (CPMR North Sea Commission, 2019).

3.7. Private sector and civil society

According to NOAA, container losses are mainly due to the non-compliance to container weights, and other safety and operational measures. The shipping industry is time-pressured, which results in a disequilibrium between safety and efficiency (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, 2014). Thus, market competitiveness pivots the balance between economy and ecology [Interview 3].

In 2019, global shipping insurer Allianz highlighted several problems on container ships, including incorrect labelling and packaging of dangerous goods and the loss of containers overboard, which accounts for one in five marine insurance claims (Allianz Global Corporate & Specialty, 2019). Allianz also mentioned that a higher accumulation of risk is due to the soaring size of vessels, and their reduced ability to manoeuvre (Degnarain, 2020; Allianz Global Corporate & Specialty, 2021). Due to globalisation, consumers can now order CPG from all parts of the world and receive them at their doorstep [Interview 3]. Therefore, the size of vessels has increased to carry more containers [Interview 3, Interview 4].

Sinking due to grounding is the most common cause of container loss (Allianz Global Corporate & Specialty, 2019). The cost of fuel determines the vessel's main cost of operations [Interview 3]. Sudden changes in shipping routes and trajectory are often done for economic reasons, with little regard to weather conditions (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, 2014) [Interview 3]. This may suggest a lack of adaption due to poor forecasting abilities of metocean¹¹ conditions, and the underestimation of these conditions in decision-making [Interview 11]. A ship crew questionnaire by MARIN in 2009 (Fig. 4) showed that extreme weather is seen as one of the main factors for cargo loss, after lashing, poor weight distribution, inaccurate weight, and rolling or the motion ability of a ship (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, 2014). Yet, climate change, the consequent ocean warming and acidification, and the melting of icebergs, will result in more fresh water in the oceans, which may lead to pattern changes and even more extreme weather conditions (NASA, 2021) [Interview 6, Interview 11].

Moreover, the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic has made

¹⁰ The circular economy is a restorative and regenerative economic system. It promotes the recycling and reuse of plastics, and the use of bio-based sources to avoid environmental externalities.

¹¹ Metocean conditions refer to the combined meteorological and oceanographic conditions, such as wind, wave and climate.

Fig. 4. Listed causes for cargo loss by ship crew. Source: MARIN (2009) as cited by National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (2014), page 15.

unprecedented changes in how people live and work, characterised by remote-work and new consumer expectations through business-to-consumer e-commerce (Wu, 2020; United Nations, 2020). Online shopping of CPG has increased exponentially and the pandemic has brought to the fore the central role of ocean-shipping for their delivery (United Nations, 2020; PwC, 2021). In 2019, the global commercial shipping fleet witnessed the highest growth rate (4.1 %) since 2014 (United Nations, 2020). This rate is expected to keep on progressing as consumer demand for CPG from emerging economies is growing (Wu, 2020) [Interview 3]. Customers are not held responsible for the loss of a container and they have limited knowledge of the supply chain behind the product ordered, or how it is transported [Interview 10]. The loss of ordered CPG at sea does not affect their ultimate delivery to the customer. CPG will be simply produced and shipped again, doubling the resources needed for a single order [Interview 6].

From the perspective of the private sector, shipping's supply chain is complex. Often producers are unaware of which ship will be transporting their goods, and as seen in the MSC Zoe case, the owner, the ship operator and the crew, are also often unaware of the contents of the containers [Interview 2]. The OECD Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) approach, of which all of the EU North Sea States are Members, extends the environmental responsibility of producers through three voluntary policy instruments that include: 1) the management of the post-consumption stage,¹² 2) performance standards,¹³ and 3) other complementary measures such as eco-labelling (Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2001; Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2020). The EPR considers the producer as the “entity with the greatest control over decisions relating to materials selection and product design”, yet, it fails to extend the producer's environmental responsibility in all phases of its supply chain, namely, in the delivery phase. Thus, while the EPR can significantly lower plastic waste, it does not address the producer's responsibility to pollution from shipping, and container loss (Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2001) [Interview 11].

¹² The EPR post-consumption management is the responsibility for producers to manage the end-of-life of their products, by implementing, for instance, a recovery and recycling system. Producers Responsibility Organisations can be hired by producers to facilitate and manage the EPR scheme.

¹³ The EPR performance standards can, for instance, establish the use of a percentage of recycled materials in production or require CPG to be designed for circularity.

Nonetheless, since the 1990s, container loss incidents began to receive media and public attention (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, 2014). Rubber ducks, washed up Nikes, and the photo of a beached whale with a littered stomach became symbols of anthropogenic waste in the oceans, which has sparked the worldwide interest of civil society (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, 2014) [Interview 1, Interview 10]. Today, various organisations such as Surfrider or The Ocean Cleanup, and documentaries, including Craig Leeson's “A Plastic Ocean”, aim to spread awareness on marine litter (Surfrider, 2021; The Ocean Cleanup, 2019; Plastic Oceans, 2020). Other projects support citizen participation in policy-making. One example is the European Environment Agency (EEA) Marine Litter-Watch, which has launched a citizen-science mobile application to report marine litter, and fill in data gaps for beach monitoring (European Environment Agency, 2015) [Interview 4].

3.8. Perceptions on the issue of container loss

When asked “who is responsible?” (for plastic pollution due to container loss), the 11 interviewees replied with multiple answers (Fig. 5). Eight respondents pointed at the ship-owner, of which three were participants with maritime law expertise. This can be explained by the relatively easier task of locating ship-owners, and thus, legally binding them to a claim. The ship operator was mentioned five times, in relation to lack of adherence to safety measures by the ship crew. The

Fig. 5. Responsibility for container loss.

P&I Clubs and the producers were mentioned four times and with an equal distribution. Reasons discussed were the traceability of P&I Clubs, as registered entities, and the responsibility of producers in making sure their merchandise is delivered safely, and in lowering their use of single-use plastics. Three answers referred to consumers' responsibility in knowing where CPG come from and how they are delivered, as well as consumerism, as a general issue of modern society.

Twenty-two obstacles to good governance in the North Sea were mentioned in the interviews (Table 1). Four general themes were recurrent, under which the number of obstacles were: governance (12), private sector (4), civil society (2), and research (4). Around 62 % of the obstacles addressed "governance", including, notably, the lack of international measures, and regulations on shipping routes to protect sensitive areas. 18 % of the obstacles were linked to the "private sector", to the soaring size of vessels, and the need to review their design and safety practices. Additionally, four of the participants raised the issue of poor transparency and labelling, which can prevent the ship crew from knowing what is inside a container, and ultimately challenge clean-up operations. 12 % of the obstacles tackled "research". Scientific research on metocean conditions was mentioned as an important preventive tool to address global warming and the ensuing extreme weather conditions, which may potentially increase the risk of casualties. Finally, 8 % of the obstacles pointed at "civil society". Interviewees mentioned the lack of involvement of civil society and the problem of intensified consumption.

4. Discussion

4.1. Synthesis

From the 263 reported incidents from 1917 to 2021, 13.3 % of worldwide spills, including oil and container spills, occurred in the North Sea. Additionally, 34 of the reported incidents occurred in

Table 1
Obstacles to current systems and processes in the North Sea.

Themes	Number of interviewees
<i>Governance</i>	
1. International measures	6
2. Regulations on shipping routes, sensitive areas	6
3. Disaster management mechanism (clean-up process and technologies)	5
4. Enforcement of existing measures	5
5. Accounting for non-values and externalities (baseline data)	4
6. Complexity of legal system and expertise	4
7. Pace of decision-making process	4
8. Prevention and monitoring	4
9. Awareness, dialogue and cooperation	4
10. Harmful substances list	4
11. Outcomes of accountability process	2
12. Fund for plastic claims	2
<i>Private sector</i>	
13. Ship size, design and safety	6
14. Transparency and labelling (contents of containers)	4
15. Use of plastics in CPG	3
16. Complexity of the supply chain	2
<i>Civil society</i>	
17. Consumerism and societal change	4
18. Involvement of civil society	2
<i>Research</i>	
19. Metocean conditions	3
20. Climate change	3
21. Future of plastics, effects and mitigation	2
22. Baseline data	1

proximity of the North Sea, and therefore could have potentially affected its waters. In total, 39 % of the reported incidents that happened in or near the North Sea were container loss cases. These numbers can be explained by the high density of traffic by cargo vessels on the route from the English Channel to the Skagerrak strait, a notable trade route.

The complexity and fragmentation of governance, and the slow-paced rhythm at which new measures are implemented, contradict with today's fast-paced and globalised world, and with the cascading effects of plastics at sea. Increased global trade and consumption patterns, and, recently, the COVID-19 pandemic, have greatly pressured the shipping sector to keep pace. Global cargo route density is growing exponentially, which is expected to impact the North Sea and the European coasts. Market demands have resulted in increased capacity of container ships, and yet, poor application of the safety guidelines, and limited manoeuvre ability due to ships' size. Time-pressure efficiency trumps weather conditions, which is a contributing factor to container spills.

Yet, the oceans are drastically heating due to greenhouse gases and other man-made pressures on planetary boundaries, which will have far-reaching effects on climate. In addition to the potential increase of extreme weather and currents in the North Sea due to global warming, the North Sea could potentially be affected by changes in ocean patterns in other areas. As seen in the analysis of spills, casualties in one location can affect other locations. Thus, the monitoring of metocean conditions locally may not be enough to forecast the future impacts of global warming in the North Sea, and, therefore, prevent container loss.

The issue of marine litter is rising on the policy agenda. Yet, no regulations were found to address the specific case of container loss, and consequent plastic pollution, at any level of governance. While some measures may apply to container spills and many initiatives seem promising, the existing legislations intersecting in the North Sea were found to be not particularly stringent. International, EU and regional Conventions count on States to adapt and enforce directives via national laws. Also, the process of proposing and enforcing new measures is long and requires lobbying efforts.

Many of the challenges encountered during oil spill claims in the 1960s and the 1970s were also observed in the contemporary cases of container spills. These challenges can be summarised in three parts: 1) the difficulty to attribute the damage to the defendant, and in supplying admissible evidence in court; 2) the issues faced in the enforcement of legal measures and the complexity of the legal system; and 3) the legal legitimacy of requiring compensation for the damage made to natural resources and the quantification of this damage in monetary terms.

In terms of responsibility, the owner and its insurer are usually the ones held accountable for a spill, since they are the easiest to track down by States. Additionally, prosecutions rarely include other parties in the supply chain, such as producers, the ship operator, or consumers. At the same time, the "Pay to be Paid" rule can limit the liability of insurers, which can be an obstacle if the owner of the vessel is unable to pay, and can result in victims paying for the clean-up costs themselves. Also, the Wakashio case underlined the importance for States to be party to the latest Conventions, especially in terms of LLMC. Moreover, linkage between a vessel and a container spill can become particularly difficult when the spill is unreported, and when CPG are released from the containers. The heterogeneous nature of plastics, and the leaching of chemicals in marine water, while also polluting, prevents the establishment of a causal link. Movements in a dynamic area can as well become an obstacle to establishing jurisdiction and to the containment of the spill due to ocean currents and gyres.

Another issue highlighted in this study is the difficulty to enforce compensation for the damage made to ecosystems and biodiversity. The societal benefits of ecosystem services has been a commonly employed concept in nature conservation policies when explaining the need for biodiversity protection and sustainable resource use (Costanza et al., 1998). Despite its popularity, the implementation of the concept into effective policy instruments and governance structures remains

challenging (Bouma and Van Beukering, 2015). Losses of non-market goods, such as recreational and biodiversity values, are difficult to quantify and to hold polluters to account for.

The “Special Areas” or the PSSA designation, which can be placed within the Precautionary Principle, apply ship routing systems to avoid sensitive areas. In theory, this could mean that Mauritius could have protected its ecosystem by applying to designate its lagoons as a PSSA. However, and as seen in the MSC Zoe case, the avoidance of routes in sensitive areas is a recommendation, as opposed to a strict regulation. Additionally, a variety of protocols and codes of practice provide guidelines for the safe transport of containers, most of which are non-mandatory. Distinct guidelines concern the handling and storing of HNS, at the exception of plastics. Furthermore, several initiatives, including the Single-Use Plastics Directive and the EPR, promote the ban on single-use plastics and recycling. Still, all man-made plastics equally threaten the environment and marine life, and stopping their production is not being considered.

4.2. Policy recommendations

The three guiding Principles embraced by North Sea States during OSPAR's NSC underpin the governance of the North Sea. Contracting Parties are required to apply the Principles, which aim to avert and eradicate marine pollution, and sustainably manage human activities.

The Precautionary Principle was one of the first principles adopted by the North Sea States (OSPAR Commission, 2021a). The precautionary principle enables decision-makers to take preventive measures when scientific evidence is uncertain and when there are reasonable grounds for concern that significant harm may be caused to the environment from anthropogenic activities (OSPAR Commission, 2021b).

Introduced by the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) in 1992, the Polluter Pays Principle is a principle for distributing the “costs of pollution prevention and control measures”. It states that when pollution is emitted, the polluter should bear all the costs for the prevention and control of emissions to protect the environment (Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, 1992). Recognised by the NSC in 1984 and included in the 1992 OSPAR Convention, the Polluter Pays Principle is an economic principle as opposed to a legal principle, polluters are therefore not bound by law to compensate the damages (Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2014). Member States are required to adopt the Polluter Pays Principle in their national laws (OSPAR Commission, 2021c).

The Ecosystem Approach is the primary framework of action under the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2021). It promotes conservation and the sustainable use of resources in an equitable way through the management of human activities. The OSPAR Commission mainly focuses on four elements within the CBD framework: raising awareness of the Ecosystem Approach, the monitoring of the marine environment, the formulation of policy and assessments, and the evaluation of human activities' impact on humans and marine life (OSPAR Commission, 2021d). In 2002, the NSC revised the Ecosystem Approach framework and pledged to implement it within the national regulations (OSPAR Commission, 2021a).

Several recommendations to the five levels of governance can be grasped from the results of this research (Table 2), listed below under the three above-mentioned NSC Principles. The recommendations aim to improve the efficiency of the systems and processes in the North Sea in addressing container spills and their consequent effects.

5. Conclusion

The aim of this paper was to gain insights into the issue of plastic pollution due to container loss and to evaluate the current systems and processes worldwide, and in the North Sea in particular. The research described the instruments and mechanisms ensuring accountability and assessed the extent to which the NSC Principles are reflected in policy.

Table 2
Recommendations of the investigation.

<i>Precautionary principle</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Strict enforcement of all existing measures o Introduction of strict homogeneous measures specific to container loss o Simplification of the system in place for an agile decision-making process o Mandatory international regulations for shipping routes o Strict legal obligation to avoid “Special Areas” and PSSA o Limitation on ship sizes and where they can sail o Mandatory transparency on the ship crew and cargo contents in a public register o Mandatory code of conduct for safety, and its revision o Placement of mandatory tracking devices technology on containers o Addition of plastics on the HNS lists o Strict regulations on the use of plastics in CPG o Development of a traceable “DNA” for each plastic used by producers o Mandatory EPR along all phases of producers' supply chain, including delivery o Additional awareness programmes on consumerism and marine litter o Review of the shipping sector's business model and pressures implied therein o Consider the possibility of banning the production of new plastics
<i>Ecosystem approach</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Monitoring of the marine environment o Gathering of baseline data through research o Further research on metocean conditions, beyond the North Sea o Further research on the effects of plastics and on clean-up technologies
<i>Polluter pays principle</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Implementation of a disaster management scheme to support and simplify the legal process o Account for non-values and the intrinsic aspect of nature in policies and legal rules o Application of stricter fines, impose sanctions or penalties for unreported spills o Application of stricter fines, impose sanctions or penalties for container loss o Revision of the LLMC and raise considerably the limitations of liability o Development of a participatory process that is inclusive of civil society o Implementation of a fund scheme, such as the IOPC, for container spills

Maritime governance is mainly reliant on global agreements, the enforcement is done via national and local governments, and the private sector is experiencing an increased pressure from all the governance levels, the nature of the trade, and from civil society. Increased human activities, and subsequent global warming, are expected to further impact the North Sea, and the world at large. These obstacles could be overcome with the enforcement and amendments of existing measures, additional measures, and further scientific research. Thus, the translation of the NSC Principles into concrete policies on container loss and a more defined accountability regime could ensure the protection of the North Sea, and the oceans, against plastic pollution.

Data availability statement

Due to the sensitive nature of the questions asked in this study during the stakeholder interviews, respondents were assured raw data would remain confidential and would not be shared.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Mayya Saliba: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Sofia Frantzi:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Pieter van Beukering:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Mendeley Data Repository was used to support this research.

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Appendix A. Analysis of worldwide casualties

Tables 3 and 4 provide insights on the magnitude of spills in the North Sea. CPG stands for all sorts of consumer-packaged goods (involving plastics), HNS stands for Hazardous and Noxious Substances, and "Containers (Unknown)" refers to incidents where information on the content spilled was not available.

Table 3 presents an extensive list of all the reported worldwide casualties from 1917 to 1921, distributed according to the region where they occurred.

Table 3

Extensive casualty list of spills by region from 1917 to 2021.

North Sea and surrounding areas			
<i>North Sea</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
1. Sitakund	England, English Channel, North Sea	October 20, 1968	Oil
2. Conoco Britannia	North Sea	June 24, 1973	Oil
3. Pacific Colocotronis	North Sea	September 22, 1975	Oil
4. Eleni V/Roseline	England, North Sea	May 6, 1978	Oil
5. Esso Bernicia/Sullom Voe	Scotland, Norwegian Sea, North Sea	December 30, 1978	Oil
6. Sindbad	Netherlands, North Sea	December 10, 1979	HNS
7. Stanislaw Dubois/Omdurman	Netherlands, North Sea	April 2, 1980	HNS
8. Sivand	England, North Sea	September 28, 1983	Oil
9. Dana Optima	North Sea	January 13, 1984	HNS
10. Mont Louis/Olau Britannia	Belgium, North Sea	August 25, 1984	Oil, HNS
11. Herald of Free Enterprise	Belgium, North Sea	March 6, 1987	HNS
12. Skyron/Hel	English Channel, North Sea	May 30, 1987	Oil
13. Anna Broere/Atlantic Compass	Netherlands, North Sea	May 27, 1988	HNS
14. Phillips Oklahoma/Fiona	North Sea	September 17, 1989	Oil
15. Stora Korsnäs Link I	England, North Sea	November 5, 1991	HNS
16. Nordfrakt	Netherlands, North Sea	October 25, 1992	HNS
17. Braer	Scotland, North Sea	January 5, 1993	Oil
18. British Trent/Western Winner	North Sea	June 3, 1993	Oil
19. Borodinskoye Polye	Scotland, North Sea	November 17, 1993	Oil
20. Sherbro	France, Netherlands, Germany, North Sea	December 8, 1993	HNS
21. Marine Trader	Netherlands, North Sea	February 14, 1994	Containers (unknown)
22. Maritime Lee	North Sea	February 27, 1996	Containers (unknown)
23. Bona Fulmar/Teoalt off Dunkirk	English Channel, North Sea	January 18, 1997	Oil
24. Renne	North Sea	February 17, 1997	Containers (unknown)
25. Apus	Netherlands, North Sea	December 17, 1998	HNS
26. Multitank Ascania	Scotland, North Sea, Norwegian Sea	March 19, 1999	HNS
27. Tricolor/Kariba	France, North Sea, English Channel	December 14, 2002	Oil, CPG
28. P&O Nedlloyd Mondriaan	Netherlands, North Sea	February 9, 2006	CPG
29. Statfjord A	Norway, North Sea	December 12, 2007	Oil
30. Godafoss	Norway, Skagerrak, North Sea	February 17, 2011	Oil, HNS
31. Flinterstar/Al Oraiq	Belgium, North Sea	October 6, 2015	Oil
32. Bow Jubail	Netherlands, North Sea	June 23, 2018	Oil
33. MSC Zoe	North Sea, Wadden Sea, Netherlands, Germany	January 1, 2019	CPG, HNS
34. Francisca	Scotland, North Sea	October 31, 2020	CPG
35. Baltic Tern	North Sea, Wadden Sea	April 7, 2021	CPG, HNS
<i>English Channel</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
36. Ocean Liberty	France, Celtic Sea, English Channel	July 23, 1947	Oil, HNS
37. Allegrity	England, English Channel	December 13, 1961	Oil
38. Pacific Glory	England, English Channel	October 10, 1970	Oil
39. Texaco Caribbean/Paracas	English Channel	January 11, 1971	Oil
40. Olympic Alliance/Royal Navy Frigate HMS Achilles	English Channel	November 12, 1975	Oil
41. Kini Kersten	France, English Channel	January 1, 1987	Oil
42. Perintis	English Channel	March 13, 1989	HNS
43. Rosebay/Diane Marie	England, English Channel	May 12, 1990	Oil
44. Grape One	English Channel	December 9, 1993	HNS

(continued on next page)

Table 3 (continued)

<i>English Channel</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
45. Ming Fortune	English Channel	April (unknown), 1994	Containers (unknown)
46. Katja	France, English Channel	August 7, 1997	Oil
47. Allegra	English Channel	October 1, 1997	HNS
48. MSC Rosa M	France, English Channel	November 30, 1997	HNS
49. Ever Decent/Norwegian Dream	England, English Channel	August 28, 1999	HNS
50. Ece/General Grot Rowecki	Guernsey, English Channel	January 2006	HNS
51. MSC Napoli	English Channel	January 18, 2007	Oil, CPG, HNS
52. Ice Prince	English Channel	January 15, 2008	Oil, CPG
53. MSC Flaminia	English Channel, international waters	July 14, 2012	HNS
54. Nijptangh	France, English Channel	October 15, 2015	Oil
<i>Kattegat, Øresund</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
55. Poona	Sweden, Kattegat	July 15, 1971	HNS
56. René 16	Sweden, Kattegat	January 16, 1976	HNS
57. Martina/Werder Bremen	Sweden, Kattegat	March 28, 2000	HNS
58. Kemira	Sweden, Øresund	February 4, 2005	HNS
<i>Celtic Sea, Bay of Biscay</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
59. Foucault	France, Bay of Biscay	September 18, 1940	Oil
60. Torrey Canyon	France, England, Celtic Sea	March 18, 1967	Oil
61. Dona Marika	Wales, Celtic Sea	August 5, 1973	Oil
62. Universe Leader	Ireland, Celtic Sea	October 22, 1974	Oil
63. Afran Zodiac	Ireland, Celtic Sea	January 11, 1975	Oil
64. Olympic Bravery	France, Celtic Sea	January 24, 1976	Oil
65. Boehlen	Sein Island, Celtic Sea	October 15, 1976	Oil
66. Amoco Cadiz	France, Celtic Sea	March 16, 1978	Oil
67. Christos Bitas	Wales, Celtic Sea	October 12, 1978	Oil
68. Betelgeuse	Ireland, Celtic Sea	January 8, 1979	Oil
69. Sea Valiant	France, Celtic Sea	March 13, 1979	Oil
70. Gino/Team Castor	France, Celtic Sea	April 28, 1979	Oil
71. Peter Sif	France, Celtic Sea	November 15, 1979	Oil
72. Tanio	France, Celtic Sea	March 7, 1980	Oil
73. MV Kowloon Bridge	Ireland, Celtic Sea	November 22, 1986	Oil
74. Brea	France, Celtic Sea	January 22, 1988	HNS
75. Amazzone	France, Celtic Sea	January 30, 1988	Oil
76. Mercedes del Mar	Bay of Biscay	December 12, 1989	Containers (unknown)
77. Sea Empress	Wales, Celtic Sea	February 15, 1996	Oil
78. Albion II	France, Celtic Sea	February 18, 1997	HNS
79. Kairo	France, Bay of Biscay	December 31, 1997	HNS
80. Junior M	France, Celtic Sea	October 4, 1999	HNS
81. Erika	France, Bay of Biscay	December 12, 1999	Oil
82. Balu	France, Bay of Biscay	March 20, 2001	HNS
83. Lykes Liberator	France, Celtic Sea	February 2, 2002	CPG, HNS
84. Norrisia	France, Celtic Sea	March 4, 2002	Oil
85. Bow Eagle	Sein Island, Celtic Sea	August 26, 2002	HNS
86. Barbaros Kiran	France, Celtic Sea	October 30, 2002	Oil
87. CMA CGM Otello	France, Bay of Biscay	February 17, 2006	CPG
88. Rokia Delmas	France, Bay of Biscay	October 24, 2006	Oil
89. Donges Refinery	France, Loire, Bay of Biscay	March 16, 2008	Oil
90. Admiral Kuznetsov	Celtic Sea	February 14, 2009	Oil
91. YM Uranus/Hanjin Rizhao	France, Celtic Sea	October 8, 2010	HNS
92. Union Neptune	France, Bay of Biscay	July 22, 2011	HNS
93. TK Bremen	France, Bay of Biscay	December 16, 2011	Oil
94. Luno	France, Bay of Biscay	February 5, 2014	Oil
95. Grande America	France, Bay of Biscay	March 10, 2019	Oil, CPG
<i>Baltic Sea</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
96. Mundogas Oslo	Gulf of Bothnia, Baltic Sea	October 22, 1966	HNS
97. Othello	Sweden, Baltic Sea	March 20, 1970	Oil
98. Amalie Essberger	Sweden, Baltic Sea	January 13, 1973	HNS
99. Martina/Werder Bremen	Sweden, Kattegat, Baltic Sea	March 28, 2000	HNS
100. Baltic Carrier/Tern	Denmark, Baltic Sea	March 29, 2001	Oil
101. Fu Shan Hai/Gdynia	Baltic Sea	May 31, 2003	Oil, HNS
102. Golden Sky	Latvia, Baltic Sea	January 15, 2007	HNS
103. Annabella	Baltic Sea	February 26, 2007	HNS

(continued on next page)

Table 3 (continued)

<i>Baltic Sea</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
104. Linda	Sweden, Baltic Sea	February 6, 2010	HNS
<i>Other areas</i>			
<i>Mediterranean Sea</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
105. Cavtat/Lady Rita	Italy, Adriatic Sea, Ionian Sea, Mediterranean Sea	July 14, 1974	HNS
106. Pavlos V	Italy, Mediterranean Sea	January 11, 1978	Oil
107. Brigitta Montanari	Croatia, Adriatic Sea, Mediterranean	November 16, 1984	HNS
108. Ocean Spirit	Malta, Mediterranean Sea	April 15, 1988	HNS
109. Sea Spirit/Hesperus	Spain, Mediterranean Sea	August 6, 1990	Oil
110. Continental Lotus	Eastern Mediterranean Sea	January 21, 1991	HNS
111. Alessandro Primo	Italy, Adriatic Sea, Mediterranean	February 1, 1991	HNS
112. Haven	Italy, Tyrrhenian Sea, Mediterranean Sea	April 11, 1991	Oil
113. Scaieni	Italy, Mediterranean Sea	December 7, 1991	HNS
114. Kaptan Manolis I	Tunisia, Tyrrhenian Sea, Mediterranean Sea	January 10, 1996	HNS
115. Anis Rose	Italy, Tyrrhenian Sea, Mediterranean Sea	January 30, 1996	HNS
116. Kira	Greece, Mediterranean Sea	February 9, 1996	Oil, HNS
117. Fenes	Corsica, Tyrrhenian Sea, Mediterranean Sea	September 25, 1996	CPG
118. Abdul Rahman	Libya, Mediterranean Sea	November 20, 1997	Oil, CPG, HNS
119. Dogruyollar IV	Italy, Tyrrhenian Sea, Mediterranean Sea	February 2, 1998	HNS
120. Enalios Thetis	Italy, Tyrrhenian Sea, Mediterranean Sea	May 6, 1999	Oil
121. CMA Djakarta	Cyprus, Mediterranean Sea	July 10, 1999	HNS
122. Rofayda	Cyprus, Mediterranean Sea	July 28, 1999	Oil, CPG
123. Eurobulker IV	Italy, Tyrrhenian Sea, Mediterranean Sea	September 8, 2000	Oil, HNS
124. Castor	Morocco, Alboran Sea, Mediterranean Sea	December 31, 2000	Oil
125. Camadan	Malta, Mediterranean Sea	March 12, 2002	HNS
126. Spabunker IV	Spain, Bay of Gibraltar, Mediterranean Sea	January 21, 2003	Oil
127. MSC Al Amine	Tunisia, Mediterranean Sea	February 15, 2005	Oil
128. New Flame/Torm Gertrud	Gibraltar, Mediterranean Sea	August, 12, 2007	Oil
129. CMA CGM Strauss/Francia	Italy, Tyrrhenian Sea, Mediterranean Sea	February 19, 2010	Oil
<i>Black Sea</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
130. Independenta/Evrialy	Turkey, Black Sea	November 15, 1979	Oil
131. Nassia/Shipbroker	Bosphorus strait, Black Sea	March 13, 1994	Oil
132. Kerch Strait	Black Sea	November 11, 2007	Oil, HNS
<i>North Atlantic Ocean</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
133. Mont Blanc/Imo	Canada, North Atlantic Ocean	December 6, 1917	CPG, HNS
134. Grandcamp	United States, Gulf of Mexico, North Atlantic Ocean	April 16, 1947	HNS
135. Janina	Portugal, North Atlantic Ocean	January 18, 1957	Oil
136. Bonifaz	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	July 3, 1964	Oil
137. Spyros Lemnos	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	November 1, 1968	Oil
138. Julius Schindler	Portugal, North Atlantic Ocean	February 11, 1969	Oil
139. Hamilton Trader/Hannes Kuppel	Irish Sea, North Atlantic Ocean	April 30, 1969	Oil
140. Al Bacruz	Portugal, North Atlantic Ocean	January 14, 1970	Oil
141. Polycommander	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	May 5, 1970	Oil
142. Erkowit/Durtmond	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	October 11, 1970	HNS
143. Golden Drake	Portugal, North Atlantic Ocean	January 28, 1972	Oil
144. Giuseppe Giuletti	Portugal, North Atlantic Ocean	April 1, 1972	Oil
145. Golar Patricia	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	November 5, 1973	Oil
146. Splendid Breeze	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	December 6, 1973	Oil
147. Jakob Maersk	Portugal, North Atlantic Ocean	January 29, 1975	Oil
148. Urquiola	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	May 12, 1976	Oil
149. Andros Patria	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	December 31, 1978	Oil
150. Kurdistan	Canada, North Atlantic Ocean	March 15, 1979	Oil
151. Atlantic Empress/Aegean Captain	Caribbean Sea, North Atlantic Ocean	July 19, 1979	Oil
152. Turgut Reis	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	December 15, 1979	Oil
153. Cason	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	December 5, 1987	HNS
154. Odyssey	Canada, North Atlantic Ocean	November 10, 1988	Oil
155. Khark 5	Spain, Morocco, North Atlantic Ocean	December 19, 1989	Oil
156. Aragon	Portugal, North Atlantic Ocean	December 29, 1989	Oil
157. Kimya	Irish Sea, North Atlantic Ocean	January 6, 1991	HNS
158. Vistabella	Caribbean Sea, near North Atlantic Ocean	March 7, 1991	Oil
159. Santa Clara I	United States, North Atlantic Ocean	January 4, 1992	HNS

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Table 3 (continued)

<i>North Atlantic Ocean</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
160. Hyderabad	U.S. East Coast, North Atlantic Ocean	January 24, 1992	Containers (unknown)
161. Jans	LaGuardia, North Atlantic Ocean	September 23, 1992	Containers (unknown)
162. Aegean Sea	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	December 3, 1992	Oil
163. Cercal	Portugal, North Atlantic Ocean	October 2, 1994	Oil
164. MSC Claudia	Boston, North Atlantic Ocean	January (unknown), 1996	Containers (unknown)
165. Ponce Trader	New Orleans, North Atlantic Ocean	September 11, 1996	Containers (unknown)
166. Igloo Moon	United States, North Atlantic Ocean	November 6, 1996	HNS
167. Pol America	Nantucket, North Atlantic Ocean	March 31, 1997	Containers (unknown)
168. MSC Carla	Portugal, North Atlantic Ocean	November 24, 1997	CPG, HNS
169. Kate Maersk	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	November (unknown), 1997	Containers (unknown)
170. MSC Rita	Nantucket, North Atlantic Ocean	December 17, 1997	Containers (unknown)
171. Dolly	Martinique, Caribbean Sea, North Atlantic Ocean	November 5, 1999	Oil
172. Guayama	Puerto Rico, Caribbean Sea, North Atlantic Ocean	December (unknown), 1999	Containers (unknown)
173. Humacao	Puerto Rico, Caribbean Sea, North Atlantic Ocean	December (unknown), 1999	Containers (unknown)
174. Ming Ocean	North Atlantic	April (unknown), 2000	Containers (unknown)
175. Coral Bulker	Portugal, North Atlantic Ocean	December 25, 2000	Oil, CPG
176. Prestige	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	November 13, 2002	Oil
177. Bow Mariner	United States, North Atlantic Ocean	February 28, 2004	HNS
178. CMA CGM Otello	France, Bay of Biscay, North Atlantic Ocean	February 17, 2006	CPG
179. CMA CGM Verdi	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	February 18, 2006	CPG
180. Eagle Otome/Barge	United States, Gulf of Mexico, North Atlantic Ocean	January 23, 2010	Oil
181. Deepwater Horizon	United States, Gulf of Mexico, North Atlantic Ocean	April 20, 2010	Oil
<i>South Atlantic Ocean</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
182. Castillo de Bellver	South Africa, South Atlantic Ocean	August 6, 1983	Oil
183. ABT Summer	Angola, South Atlantic Ocean	May 28, 1991	Oil
184. San Jorge	Uruguay, South Atlantic Ocean	February 8, 1997	Oil
185. Treasure	South Africa, South Atlantic Ocean	June 26, 2000	Oil
186. Vicuña	Brazil, South Atlantic Ocean	November 15, 2004	Oil, HNS
187. Oliva	Tristan da Cunha, South Atlantic Ocean	March 16, 2011	Oil, CPG
<i>Indian Ocean</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
188. Oceanic Grandeur	Australia, Indian Ocean	March 3, 1970	Oil
189. Sea Star	Gulf of Oman, Indian Ocean	December 19, 1972	Oil
190. Princess Anne Marie	Australia, Indian Ocean	July 14, 1975	Oil
191. Ariadne	Somalia, Indian Ocean	August 24, 1985	HNS
192. Korean Star	Australia, Indian Ocean	May 20, 1988	Oil
193. Kirki	Australia, Indian Ocean	July 21, 1991	Oil
194. Katina P	Mozambique, Indian Ocean	April 16, 1992	Oil
195. Era	Australia, Indian Ocean	August 30, 1992	Oil
196. Infiniti	Curaçao, Caribbean Sea, Indian Ocean	July 31, 1995	CPG
197. Leerort	Indian Ocean	September 19, 1998	Containers (unknown)
198. Natuna Sea	Indonesia, Indian Ocean	October 3, 2000	Oil
199. CMA CGM Normandie	Singapore Strait, Indian Ocean	March 27, 2001	CPG
200. Hanjin Pennsylvania	Indian Ocean	November 11, 2002	HNS
201. Tasman Spirit	Pakistan, Arabian Sea, Indian Ocean	July 27, 2003	Oil
202. Adamandas	Reunion Island, Indian Ocean	September 22, 2003	HNS
203. Al Samidoun	Egypt, Suez Canal, Red Sea, Indian Ocean	December 14, 2004	Oil
204. Tugen	Madagascar, Indian Ocean	February 3, 2006	Oil
205. Hyundai Fortune	Gulf of Aden, Indian Ocean	March 21, 2006	HNS
206. Bright Artemis	Persian Gulf, Indian Ocean	August 14, 2006	Oil
207. Granba	Sri Lanka, Indian Ocean	April 9, 2009	HNS
208. Gülser Ana	Madagascar, Indian Ocean	August 26, 2009	Oil, HNS
209. MSC Chitra/MV Khalijia II	India, Arabian Sea, Indian Ocean	August 07, 2010	Oil, HNS
210. Rak Carrier	India, Indian Ocean	August 4, 2011	Oil
211. Tycoon	Australia, Indian Ocean	January 8, 2012	Oil, HNS

(continued on next page)

Table 3 (continued)

<i>Indian Ocean</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
212. Stolt Valor	Persian Gulf, Indian Ocean	March 16, 2012	Oil, HNS
213. MOL Comfort	Indian Ocean	June 17, 2013	Oil, HNS
214. MSC Palak	South Africa, Indian Ocean	July 14, 2020	CPG
215. MV Wakashio	Mauritius, Indian Ocean	July 25, 2020	Oil
216. X-Press Pearl	Sri Lanka, Indian Ocean	May 27, 2021	Oil, CPG, HNS
<i>Pacific Ocean</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
217. Sygna	Australia, South Pacific Ocean	May 26, 1974	Oil
218. Yuyo Maru N°10/Pacific Alice	Japan, North Pacific Ocean	November 9, 1974	HNS
219. Lindenbank	Kiribati, North Pacific Ocean	August 17, 1975	HNS
220. Irenes Challenge	North Pacific Ocean	January 18, 1977	Oil
221. Hawaiian Patriot	Honolulu, North Pacific Ocean	February 23, 1977	Oil
222. World Encouragement	Australia, Tasman Sea, South Pacific Ocean	September 10, 1979	Oil
223. Exxon Valdez	Alaska, North Pacific Ocean	March 24, 1989	Oil
224. Hansa Carrier	Canada, Alaska, international, North Pacific	January 4, 1990	CPG
225. Ever Laurel	Alaska, North Pacific Ocean, international	January, 10, 1992	CPG
226. Uni-Humanity	Hong Kong, West Pacific Ocean	October 23, 1992	Containers (unknown)
227. Stella 1	Hong Kong, West Pacific Ocean	October 27, 1992	Containers (unknown)
228. N°1 Chung Mu/N°1 Chon Stone	China, South China Sea, North West Pacific Ocean	March 9, 1995	HNS
229. Alexandria III	South Korea, West Pacific Ocean	June 30, 1995	Containers (unknown)
230. Sea Prince	Korea, Japan, East China Sea, Sea of Japan, West Pacific Ocean	July 23, 1995	Oil
231. Nakhodka	Japan, North Pacific Ocean	January 2, 1997	Oil
232. Konemu	New Caledonia, South Pacific Ocean	January 23, 1997	Oil
233. Sealand Pacific	Pacific Ocean	January 20, 1998	Containers (unknown)
234. Koon Hong 211	Hong Kong, West Pacific Ocean	April 21, 1998	Containers (unknown)
235. APL China	Pacific Ocean	October (unknown), 1998	Containers (unknown)
236. President Adams	Mid-Pacific Ocean	October (unknown), 1998	Containers (unknown)
237. Ever Union	Mid-Pacific Ocean	October (unknown), 1998	Containers (unknown)
238. Ever Given	Mid-Pacific Ocean	October (unknown), 1998	Containers (unknown)
239. Union Rotoiti	New Zealand, South Pacific Ocean	April 26, 1999	Containers (unknown)
240. Laura d'Amato	Australia, South Pacific Ocean	August 3, 1999	Oil
241. OOCL America	Mid-Pacific Ocean	January 26, 2000	Containers (unknown)
242. Choyang Honour	Mid-Pacific Ocean	February 4, 2000	Containers (unknown)
243. Bunga Teratai Satu	Australia, Coral Sea, West Pacific Ocean	November 2, 2000	HNS
244. Jessica	Ecuador, South Pacific Ocean	January 16, 2001	Oil
245. Co-op Venture	Japan, Shibushi Bay, North Pacific Ocean	July 25, 2002	Oil, CPG
246. Selendang Ayu	Alaska, North Pacific Ocean	December 7, 2004	Oil
247. Solar 1	Philippines, West Pacific Ocean	August 11, 2006	Oil
248. Hebei Spirit/Samsung 1	South Korea, West Pacific Ocean	December 7, 2007	Oil
249. Princess of the Stars	Philippines, West Pacific Ocean	June 21, 2008	Oil, HNS
250. Pacific Adventurer	Australia, Coral Sea, South Pacific Ocean	March 11, 2009	Oil, HNS
251. Shen Neng 1	Australia, Coral Sea, South Pacific Ocean	April 3, 2010	Oil, HNS
252. Rena	New Zealand, South Pacific Ocean	October 5, 2011	Oil, HNS
253. Bareli	China, North Pacific Ocean	March 15, 2012	Oil, HNS
254. Bunga Alpina	Malaysia, South China Sea, West Pacific Ocean	July 26, 2012	Oil
255. Asian Lily	Papua New-Guinea, South Pacific Ocean	December 24, 2012	Oil
256. CMA CGM Florida/Chou Shan	China, East China Sea, West Pacific Ocean	March 18, 2013	Oil
257. TS Taipei	Taiwan, East China Sea, West Pacific Ocean	March 10, 2016	Oil
258. MT Sanchi	China, East China Sea, West Pacific Ocean	January 6, 2018	Oil
259. ONE Apus	Pacific Ocean	November 30, 2020	CPG, HNS
260. MV Ever Liberal	Japan, West Pacific Ocean	December 30, 2020	CPG
261. Maersk Essen	Pacific Ocean	January 16, 2021	CPG
262. Maersk Eindhoven	Pacific Ocean	February 17, 2021	CPG
263. A Symphony/Sea Justice	China, Yellow Sea, West Pacific Ocean	April 27, 2021	Oil

Table 4 highlights the reported worldwide casualties from 1917 to 1921 that involved container losses.

Table 4
Casualty list of container loss from 1917 to 2021.

North Sea and surrounding areas			
<i>North Sea</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
1. Sindbad	Netherlands, North Sea	December 10, 1979	HNS
2. Stanislaw Dubois/Omdurman	Netherlands, North Sea	April 2, 1980	HNS
3. Dana Optima	North Sea	January 13, 1984	HNS
4. Mont Louis/Olau Britannia	Belgium, North Sea	August 25, 1984	Oil, HNS
5. Herald of Free Enterprise	Belgium, North Sea	March 6, 1987	HNS
6. Anna Broere/Atlantic Compass	Netherlands, North Sea	May 27, 1988	HNS
7. Stora Korsnäs Link I	England, North Sea	November 5, 1991	HNS
8. Nordfrakt	Netherlands, North Sea	October 25, 1992	HNS
9. Sherbro	France, Netherlands, Germany, North Sea	December 8, 1993	HNS
10. Marine Trader	Netherlands, North Sea	February 14, 1994	Containers (unknown)
11. Maritime Lee	North Sea	February 27, 1996	Containers (unknown)
12. Renne	North Sea	February 17, 1997	Containers (unknown)
13. Apus	Netherlands, North Sea	December 17, 1998	HNS
14. Multitank Ascania	Scotland, North Sea, Norwegian Sea	March 19, 1999	HNS
15. Tricolor/Kariba	France, North Sea, English Channel	December 14, 2002	Oil, other
16. P&O Nedlloyd Mondriaan	Netherlands, North Sea	February 9, 2006	Other
17. Godafoss	Norway, Skagerrak, North Sea	February 17, 2011	Oil, HNS
18. MSC Zoe	North Sea, Wadden Sea	January 1, 2019	Other, HNS
19. Francisca	Scotland, North Sea	October 31, 2020	Other
20. Baltic Tern	North Sea, Wadden Sea	April 7, 2021	Other, HNS
<i>English Channel</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
21. Ocean Liberty	France, Celtic Sea, English Channel	July 23, 1947	Oil, HNS
22. Perintis	English Channel	March 13, 1989	HNS
23. Grape One	English Channel	December 9, 1993	HNS
24. Ming Fortune	English Channel	April (unknown), 1994	Containers (unknown)
25. Allegra	English Channel	October 1, 1997	HNS
26. MSC Rosa M	France, English Channel	November 30, 1997	HNS
27. Ever Decent/Norwegian Dream	England, English Channel	August 28, 1999	HNS
28. Ece/General Grot Rowecki	Guernsey, English Channel	January 2006	HNS
29. MSC Napoli	English Channel	January 18, 2007	Oil, other, HNS
30. Ice Prince	English Channel	January 15, 2008	Oil, other
31. MSC Flaminia	English Channel, international waters	July 14, 2012	HNS
<i>Celtic Sea, Bay of Biscay</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
32. Brea	France, Celtic Sea	January 22, 1988	HNS
33. Mercedes del Mar	Bay of Biscay	December 12, 1989	Containers (unknown)
34. Albion II	France, Celtic Sea	February 18, 1997	HNS
35. Kairo	France, Bay of Biscay	December 31, 1997	HNS
36. Junior M	France, Celtic Sea	October 4, 1999	HNS
37. Balu	France, Bay of Biscay	March 20, 2001	HNS
38. Lykes Liberator	France, Celtic Sea	February 2, 2002	Other, HNS
39. Bow Eagle	Sein Island, Celtic Sea	August 26, 2002	HNS
40. CMA CGM Otello	France, Bay of Biscay	February 17, 2006	Other
41. YM Uranus/Hanjin Rizhao	France, Celtic Sea	October 8, 2010	HNS
42. Union Neptune	France, Bay of Biscay	July 22, 2011	HNS
43. Grande America	France, Bay of Biscay	March 10, 2019	Oil, other
<i>Kattegat, Øresund</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
44. Poona	Sweden, Kattegat	July 15, 1971	HNS
45. René 16	Sweden, Kattegat	January 16, 1976	HNS
46. Martina/Werder Bremen	Sweden, Kattegat	March 28, 2000	HNS
47. Kemira	Sweden, Øresund	February 4, 2005	HNS
<i>Baltic Sea</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
48. Mundogas Oslo	Gulf of Bothnia, Baltic Sea	October 22, 1966	HNS
49. Amalie Essberger	Sweden, Baltic Sea	January 13, 1973	HNS
50. Martina/Werder Bremen	Sweden, Kattegat, Baltic Sea	March 28, 2000	HNS
51. Fu Shan Hai/Gdynia	Baltic Sea	May 31, 2003	Oil, HNS
52. Golden Sky	Latvia, Baltic Sea	January 15, 2007	HNS
53. Annabella	Baltic Sea	February 26, 2007	HNS
54. Linda	Sweden, Baltic Sea	February 6, 2010	HNS

(continued on next page)

Table 4 (continued)

<i>Baltic Sea</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
<i>Mediterranean Sea</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
55. Cavtat/Lady Rita	Italy, Adriatic Sea, Ionian Sea, Mediterranean Sea	July 14, 1974	HNS
56. Brigitta Montanari	Croatia, Adriatic Sea, Mediterranean	November 16, 1984	HNS
57. Ocean Spirit	Malta, Mediterranean Sea	April 15, 1988	HNS
58. Continental Lotus	Eastern Mediterranean Sea	January 21, 1991	HNS
59. Alessandro Primo	Italy, Adriatic Sea, Mediterranean	February 1, 1991	HNS
60. Scaieni	Italy, Mediterranean Sea	December 7, 1991	HNS
61. Kaptan Manolis I	Tunisia, Tyrrhenian Sea, Mediterranean Sea	January 10, 1996	HNS
62. Anis Rose	Italy, Tyrrhenian Sea, Mediterranean Sea	January 30, 1996	HNS
63. Kira	Greece, Mediterranean Sea	February 9, 1996	Oil, HNS
64. Fenes	Corsica, Tyrrhenian Sea, Mediterranean Sea	September 25, 1996	Other
65. Abdul Rahman	Libya, Mediterranean Sea	November 20, 1997	Oil, other, HNS
66. Dogruyollar IV	Italy, Tyrrhenian Sea, Mediterranean Sea	February 2, 1998	HNS
67. CMA Djakarta	Cyprus, Mediterranean Sea	July 10, 1999	HNS
68. Rofayda	Cyprus, Mediterranean Sea	July 28, 1999	Oil, other
69. Eurobulker IV	Italy, Tyrrhenian Sea, Mediterranean Sea	September 8, 2000	Oil, HNS
70. Camadan	Malta, Mediterranean Sea	March 12, 2002	HNS
<i>Black Sea</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
71. Kerch Strait	Black Sea	November 11, 2007	Oil, HNS
<i>North Atlantic Ocean</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
72. Mont Blanc/Imo	Canada, North Atlantic Ocean	December 6, 1917	Other, HNS
73. Grandcamp	United States, Gulf of Mexico, North Atlantic Ocean	April 16, 1947	HNS
74. Erkowit/Durtmond	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	October 11, 1970	HNS
75. Cason	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	December 5, 1987	HNS
76. Kimya	Irish Sea, North Atlantic Ocean	January 6, 1991	HNS
77. Santa Clara I	United States, North Atlantic Ocean	January 4, 1992	HNS
78. Hyderabad	U.S. East Coast, North Atlantic Ocean	January 24, 1992	Containers (unknown)
79. Jans	LaGuardia, North Atlantic Ocean	September 23, 1992	Containers (unknown)
80. MSC Claudia	Boston, North Atlantic Ocean	January (unknown), 1996	Containers (unknown)
81. Ponce Trader	New Orleans, North Atlantic Ocean	September 11, 1996	Containers (unknown)
82. Igloo Moon	United States, North Atlantic Ocean	November 6, 1996	HNS
83. Pol America	Nantucket, North Atlantic Ocean	March 31, 1997	Containers (unknown)
84. MSC Carla	Portugal, North Atlantic Ocean	November 24, 1997	Other, HNS
85. Kate Maersk	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	November (unknown), 1997	Containers (unknown)
86. MSC Rita	Nantucket, North Atlantic Ocean	December 17, 1997	Containers (unknown)
87. Guayama	Puerto Rico, Caribbean Sea, North Atlantic Ocean	December (unknown), 1999	Containers (unknown)
88. Humacao	Puerto Rico, Caribbean Sea, North Atlantic Ocean	December (unknown), 1999	Containers (unknown)
89. Ming Ocean	North Atlantic	April (unknown), 2000	Containers (unknown)
90. Coral Bulker	Portugal, North Atlantic Ocean	December 25, 2000	Oil, other
91. Bow Mariner	United States, North Atlantic Ocean	February 28, 2004	HNS
92. CMA CGM Otello	France, Bay of Biscay, North Atlantic Ocean	February 17, 2006	Other
93. CMA CGM Verdi	Spain, North Atlantic Ocean	February 18, 2006	Other
<i>Other areas</i>			
<i>South Atlantic Ocean</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
94. Vicuña	Brazil, South Atlantic Ocean	November 15, 2004	Oil, HNS
95. Oliva	Tristan da Cunha, South Atlantic Ocean	March 16, 2011	Oil, other
<i>Indian Ocean</i>			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
96. Ariadne	Somalia, Indian Ocean	August 24, 1985	HNS
97. Infiniti	Curaçao, Caribbean Sea, Indian Ocean	July 31, 1995	Other
98. Leerort	Indian Ocean	September 19, 1998	Containers (unknown)
99. CMA CGM Normandie	Singapore Strait, Indian Ocean	March 27, 2001	Other
100. Hanjin Pennsylvania	Indian Ocean	November 11, 2002	HNS
101. Adamandas	Reunion Island, Indian Ocean	September 22, 2003	HNS
102. Hyundai Fortune	Gulf of Aden, Indian Ocean	March 21, 2006	HNS
103. Granba	Sri Lanka, Indian Ocean	April 9, 2009	HNS
104. Gülsar Ana	Madagascar, Indian Ocean	August 26, 2009	Oil, HNS
105. MSC Chitra/MV Khalijia II	India, Arabian Sea, Indian Ocean	August 07, 2010	Oil, HNS

(continued on next page)

Table 4 (continued)

Indian Ocean			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
106. Tycoon	Australia, Indian Ocean	January 8, 2012	Oil, HNS
107. Stolt Valor	Persian Gulf, Indian Ocean	March 16, 2012	Oil, HNS
108. MOL Comfort	Indian Ocean	June 17, 2013	Oil, HNS
109. MSC Palak	South Africa, Indian Ocean	July 14, 2020	Other
110. X-Press Pearl	Sri Lanka, Indian Ocean	May 27, 2021	Oil, other, HNS
Pacific Ocean			
Vessel	Location	Date	Type of spill
111. Yuyo Maru N°10/Pacific Alice	Japan, North Pacific Ocean	November 9, 1974	HNS
112. Lindenbank	Kiribati, North Pacific Ocean	August 17, 1975	HNS
113. Hansa Carrier	Canada, Alaska, international, North Pacific	January 4, 1990	Other
114. Ever Laurel	Alaska, North Pacific Ocean, international	January, 10, 1992	Other
115. Uni-Humanity	Hong Kong, West Pacific Ocean	October 23, 1992	Containers (unknown)
116. Stella 1	Hong Kong, West Pacific Ocean	October 27, 1992	Containers (unknown)
117. N°1 Chung Mu/N°1 Chon Stone	China, South China Sea, North West Pacific Ocean	March 9, 1995	HNS
118. Alexandria III	South Korea, West Pacific Ocean	June 30, 1995	Containers (unknown)
119. Sealand Pacific	Pacific Ocean	January 20, 1998	Containers (unknown)
120. Koon Hong 211	Hong Kong, West Pacific Ocean	April 21, 1998	Containers (unknown)
121. APL China	Pacific Ocean	October (unknown), 1998	Containers (unknown)
122. President Adams	Mid-Pacific Ocean	October (unknown), 1998	Containers (unknown)
123. Ever Union	Mid-Pacific Ocean	October (unknown), 1998	Containers (unknown)
124. Ever Given	Mid-Pacific Ocean	October (unknown), 1998	Containers (unknown)
125. Union Rotoiti	New Zealand, South Pacific Ocean	April 26, 1999	Containers (unknown)
126. OOCL America	Mid-Pacific Ocean	January 26, 2000	Containers (unknown)
127. Choyang Honour	Mid-Pacific Ocean	February 4, 2000	Containers (unknown)
128. Bunga Teratai Satu	Australia, Coral Sea, West Pacific Ocean	November 2, 2000	HNS
129. Co-op Venture	Japan, Shibushi Bay, North Pacific Ocean	July 25, 2002	Oil, other
130. Princess of the Stars	Philippines, West Pacific Ocean	June 21, 2008	Oil, HNS
131. Pacific Adventurer	Australia, Coral Sea, South Pacific Ocean	March 11, 2009	Oil, HNS
132. Shen Neng 1	Australia, Coral Sea, South Pacific Ocean	April 3, 2010	Oil, HNS
133. Rena	New Zealand, South Pacific Ocean	October 5, 2011	Oil, HNS
134. Bareli	China, North Pacific Ocean	March 15, 2012	Oil, HNS
135. ONE Apus	Pacific Ocean	November 30, 2020	Other, HNS
136. MV Ever Liberal	Japan, West Pacific Ocean	December 30, 2020	Other
137. Maersk Essen	Pacific Ocean	January 16, 2021	Other
138. Maersk Eindhoven	Pacific Ocean	February 17, 2021	Other

Appendix B. Interview participants

Table 5

List of participants.

Interview number	Name	Position	Expertise
1	Anonymous	Representative, Marine Environment and Water Industry, European Commission	EU
2	Edward Brans	Attorney in charge of the MSC Zoe lawsuit; Professor of Sustainability and Environmental Liability, Utrecht University	Maritime Law
3	Mike Mannaart	Secretary, Kommunernes Internationale Miljøorganisation	Regional
4	Monika Peterlin	Expert Sustainability Transitions for Oceans and Freshwater, European Environment Agency	EU
5	Mareike Erfeling	Representative, OSPAR Commission; Marine Strategy Framework Directive, Rijkswaterstaat	Regional and National
6	Astrid Fischer	Research Fellow in Analytical Chemistry, School of Biological and Marine Sciences, University of Plymouth	Marine Science
7	Anonymous	Representative, Common Wadden Sea Secretariat	Local
8	Nol van Hal	Attorney on Maritime Law, Specialised in Ship Collisions, Salvage, Limitation of Liability, Shipbuilding, Ship Arrests, Marine Insurance and Offshore Contracting	Maritime Law
9	Ann Toft	Ex-Chairwoman, North Sea Network of Investigators and Prosecutors; Senior Consultant, Danish Environmental Board of Appeal (present)	Maritime Law
10	Yolanda Schmal	Policy Advisor Circular Economy, North Sea Commission; Representative, Provincie Noord-Holland	Regional and National
11	Patrycja Enet	United Nations International Expert — UN Secretariat of the Environment Management Group, United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change Secretariat; EU MSP Expert North Sea focal point, European MSP Assistance Mechanism of the European Commission; Senior Advisor at Aktis Hydraulics.	Global and Regional

Appendix C. Interview protocol

Table 6
Interview questionnaire 1 — *Governance measures.*

General question
1. Can you tell me briefly about your involvement in the efforts to reduce marine litter?
Shipping spill prevention
2. Can you give a few examples of existing measures (e.g. technologies, initiatives, regulations), at the local, national, EU, regional and global levels to prevent risks of cargo loss by ships in the North Sea?
3. In your opinion, are these measures sufficient?
4. Do you think there are other types of measures that could help prevent risks of cargo loss? If yes, which?
Shipping spill mitigation
5. In the case of a cargo ship spill, who, in your opinion, should be liable for the potential damage, and to whom?
6. Can you give a few examples of existing measures at the local, national, EU, regional and global levels for holding the responsible entity (or entities) to account in the event of a cargo ship spill?
7. In your opinion, are these measures proportional to the damage made?
8. Do you think there should be additional measures to mitigate the damage made by cargo loss? If yes, which?
Shipping spill incidents
9. What would you say are the main differences (if any) between the legal/policy response to a plastic spill incident and other types of spill incidents, for example an oil or chemical spill?
Final question – Shipping spill management
10. Do you have any other recommendations to better protect the North Sea from plastic pollution due to cargo ship spills?
Additional questions
11. In your view, what are the main repercussions of a cargo ship spill incident on the environment and on society?
12. What would you say are the main differences (if any) between the effects of a plastic spill incident and the effects of other types of spill incidents, for example an oil or chemical spill?
13. Would you say the responsibility in the event of a cargo loss is fairly spread? Please explain?
14. Who, in your opinion, should assess the amount of money needed to compensate for the damage caused by a cargo ship spill, and how should this amount be calculated?
15. What would you say are the main challenges experienced during negotiations between the responsible entity (or entities) and the plaintiff(s)?

Table 7
Interview questionnaire 2 — *Claims and legal rules.*

General question
1. Can you tell me briefly about your involvement in the efforts to reduce marine litter?
Shipping spill mitigation
2. What are the requirements for a shipping spill (e.g. oil, containers, chemicals) to qualify for a legal claim?
3. In the case of a cargo ship spill, who, in your opinion, should be liable for the potential damage, and to whom? In your experience, has this been the case?
4. In the case of a cargo ship spill, through what processes is the responsible party held into account in the North Sea?
5. What are the possible outcomes of these processes? And how is accountability being enforced on the responsible party?
6. In your opinion, are the outcomes of accountability (e.g. penalties, sanctions, monetary compensation) for the responsible party proportional to the damage they have made?
7. When monetary compensation is one of these outcomes, who, in your opinion, should assess the amount the responsible party should pay, and how do you think this amount should be calculated?
8. What would you say are the main challenges faced during cases of shipping spills?
9. What would you say are the main challenges experienced during negotiations between the responsible party and the plaintiff?
10. What would you say are the main differences (if any) between the legal response and accountability processes involved in a plastic spill incident and other types of spill incidents, for example an oil or chemical spill?
Final question
11. Do you have any other recommendations to better protect the North Sea from plastic pollution due to cargo ship spills?
Possible additional questions
12. Do you think there should be additional measures to prevent or mitigate the damage made by cargo loss? If yes, which?
13. Would you say the responsibility in the event of a cargo loss is fairly spread? Please explain?

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